

**STATE ADMINISTRATION DURING THE REIGN OF
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17358405>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 11th October 2025Accepted: 13th October 2025Online: 15th October 2025**KEYWORDS***Sahibkiran, Savior of our homeland, sadr, mutawalli, shaykhul-Islam, qazi, mufti, muhtasib, judicial-legal system.***ABSTRACT**

This article vividly demonstrates Amir Temur's accomplishments in state administration, as well as his internal and external policies, which led to the strengthening of his empire in his time. It also shows how the comprehensive reforms being implemented in the Independent Republic of Uzbekistan, which is currently flourishing, strengthen the country's confidence in its future in the field of governance, and how the rich experience of the great Sahibkiran Amir Temur is being deeply studied and applied in practice today.

Introduction.

We know that Central Asia was considered among the dependent states of the Tsarist Russian government from 1920 to 1990. For this reason, various measures were applied during this period with the aim of subjugating colonial countries and destroying entire nations. For example, policies of opposing national identity, repressing national intellectuals and Jadids, and distorting history were pursued. Among these, our great ancestor, the Sahibkiran, was also portrayed as an evil, cruel, and merciless person. However, after the period of independence, a number of measures were taken to clear Amir Temur's name. Specifically, based on the policy of our state and the will of our people, the Cabinet of Ministers adopted a resolution "On celebrating the 660th anniversary of Amir Temur's birth" on December 29, 1994, and on December 26, 1995, the President issued a decree "On declaring 1996 as the Year of Amir Temur." In March 1996, decrees were issued on establishing the "History of the Timurids" State Museum and instituting the "Amir Temur" Order. Based on UNESCO's decision, the 660th anniversary of Amir Temur's birth was widely celebrated worldwide. In April 1996, a scientific conference on "The Flourishing of Science, Culture, and Education during the Timurid Era" was held at the UNESCO headquarters in Paris, where a high appraisal was given to the Great Statesman's place in history. "Amir Temur left his name in history as a great commander and statesman who built a powerful and flourishing state in world history.

During the 14th-15th centuries, even the Mongols could not pose a threat to the state built by Amir Temur, because the Sahibkiran was considered the strongest commander of his time. Furthermore, during the reign of Amir Temur and the Timurids, as in all Islamic countries, Islamic Sharia was the basis of the judicial-legal system. The administration of

Sharia ordinances was entrusted to the country's chief Qazi (judge), and the activities of his courts in the provinces were carried out by provincial Qazis. A separate military-judicial system existed for the army, which was managed by Qazi-Askars – military judges. Other officials such as Sheikhul-Islam, Sadr, Mufti, Mutawalli, Muhtasib also played a significant role in the judicial-legal system. The Qazi monitored the law in every city and province, and at various levels of the Divan (council). Qazis differed from each other according to their rank and status. Sadrs were mostly individuals from Sayyid families, and they led the Muslim community. One of their most important duties was to supervise the country's endowments (waqfs). Sadrs also determined suyurghals (land grants). Mutawalli was a person appointed by the Sadrs to manage and supervise waqfs. The Sahibkiran Amir Temur, responding to the demands and needs of his era, perfected state administration, giving it a new spirit and content. Although the state's structural organization was based on military-political orders, it also aimed at the development of society and ensuring the interests of all social strata. In Amir Temur's empire, state administration consisted of two bodies: the Dargoh and the Vazirlik (Devon - ministry/council). The Dargoh was headed by the Supreme Ruler himself. The executive power the Divan was headed by the Devonbegi (chief vizier). Within the Divan, there were a military minister, a minister for property and tax affairs, and a finance minister. In addition to these, there were three more ministers responsible for the administration of borders and dependent countries, who reported to the Devonbegi. There were a thousand foot and a thousand mounted messengers (choparlar) who kept informed of external and internal extraordinary events. Yamkhanas (post stations) were established throughout the empire at intervals of a day's journey. Each yam kept 50–200 horses. The Sahibkiran relied on his close associates in governing the country. The Sahibkiran based his state administration on Islamic laws and rules. His attitude towards the Holy Quran and Hadith was sincere and of the highest regard. He held boundless respect for the descendants of the Prophet and the Sheikhul-Mashayikh (spiritual leaders). He relied on such individuals in strengthening the state. In addition, with the aim of conveying to his descendants which areas of state administration required more attention, the Sahibkiran wrote a book based on his daily life and named it "Temur's Code" (Temur Tuzuklari). This book, in fact, belongs to the category of books that every head of state should read. Specifically, according to Temur's Code:

- If any soldier (sipahi) exceeded his bounds and oppressed a subordinate, he was handed over to the oppressed person, and that oppressed person himself punished the soldier.
- If a treasurer committed treason in financial matters, after investigation, if the amount misappropriated by the responsible person exceeded their salary by more than double, the excess was withheld from their future wages.
- If a village elder or city dignitary oppressed a person of lower status, a large fine commensurate with the severity of the oppression was imposed.
- A military individual who committed oppression against the populace either paid a fine or was flogged with a whip.
- Anyone who committed theft, stealing another's property, was required to return it or faced severe punishment in accordance with the Yasa.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, the Sahibkiran, who contributed to world civilization, became a clear example for subsequent generations. This enlightened individual was not only a commander but also a great thinker.

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